

The Impact of Green Recruitment and Selection Practices on Corporate Sustainability: Evidence from Manufacturing Companies in Cameroon

Enanalor Lucy Obie ✉

Department of Management Science, Faculty of Social and Management Sciences University of Buea, Cameroon

Michael Forzeh Fossung

Department of Accounting, Faculty of Social and Management Sciences, University of Buea, Cameroon

Nkoa Bruno Emmanuel Ongo

Department of Economics, Faculty of Social and Management Science, University of Buea Cameroon

Abstract

In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the importance of sustainable practices in the business sector. Manufacturing companies, in particular, have a significant impact on the environment due to their resource consumption, waste generation, and greenhouse gas emissions. As a result, there is a need to explore and implement sustainable strategies to mitigate the environmental impact of manufacturing operations. Human resource management practices play a crucial role in shaping organisational behavior and culture. Green HRM practices, specifically, focus on incorporating sustainable principles and environmental considerations into HR policies, processes, and activities. Despite increasing global awareness of environmental issues and the imperative for sustainable business practices, there remains a gap in knowledge regarding the specific effects of green HRM practices on corporate sustainability within the manufacturing sector in Cameroon. Therefore, this study sought to investigate the effects of green recruitment and selection practices on corporate sustainability in Manufacturing Companies in Cameroon. The study adopted a mixed research design. Data for this study was gotten with the help of a structured questionnaire and which was analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Results from the partial least square application process, paperless recruitment telephone and video-based interviews had positive and statistically significant influence on corporate sustainability. It is recommended that companies should implement online advertisement and paperless recruitment methods to attract environmentally conscious candidates and reduce the environmental footprint of the recruitment process. Also from the findings, the study recommends that the companies should continue to explore innovative recruitment methods, such as telephone video-based interviews, to assess candidates' alignment with sustainability values and practices.

Keywords: *Green HRM, Green recruitment, selection process, corporate sustainability.*

JEL Classification codes: *O15, Q01, Q56.*

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Introduction

In the past, merely fulfilling economic performance alone was vital to ensuring the success of an organisation, but this traditional standpoint is not compatible with society's current demands, as there is increasing social pressure on organisations to become more sustainable. The evidence of adverse environmental impacts of the activities of these organisations especially the manufacturing companies has been of concern to the government, organisations, and the host communities where they operate (Ullah, 2017). These activities have not only caused degradation to the environment but also have destroyed the traditional livelihood of the region as well as environmental pollution that has affected weather conditions, soil fertility waterways aquatic habitats and wildlife most especially in Africa, where many firms in the manufacturing industry adopt different managerial concepts for practices with less consideration of its effects on the environment (Osuagwu, 2006).

Owing to the harmful consequences of industrial pollution there is the need for manufacturing companies to imbibe sustainable practices which not only support green environment but one which also supports their social goals. This is mainly built on an undeniable fact that organisations through their daily operations contribute most of the carbon footprints that adversely impact on the environment (Liu, 2010). The challenge of climate disruption and natural resource depletion is a global challenge society is facing. It is everyone's responsibility to monitor their carbon footprints and to conserve the limited natural resources we have. As part of Cameroon's economic diversification initiatives, the manufacturing sector has grown in prominence. To this end, the study's goal is to find answers to the following question.

What is the effect of green recruitment and selection on sustainability of manufacturing companies in Cameroon? (2) Objectives of the Study is to investigate the effect of green recruitment and selection on sustainability in manufacturing companies in Cameroon. The Hypothesis of the study is Green recruitment and selection has a positive influence on corporate sustainability in manufacturing companies in Cameroon.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

The study used three different research designs. That is causal design, survey design, and cross-sectional design. Hussein (2009) argued that combining different research designs into one study increases the validity of the findings. A combination of different research designs is referred to as triangulation. Different methods are used to accept or reject this hypothesis. In this study, a survey methodology to collect data from a sample of employees in manufacturing firms in Cameroon. The data was analyzed using statistical methods to test our hypotheses and draw conclusions about the effect of green recruitment and selection on sustainability of manufacturing companies

Population of the Study

The population for this study is manufacturing firms in Cameroon. This study intends to determine the extent to which green recruitment and selection may influence the sustainability of Cameroon's large manufacturing enterprises.

Sampling Procedures and Sample Size

Sampling procedures

The sampling technique used in this study was simple random sampling. The reason for using a sample random sampling is that the population of interest is difficult to access, and it would be challenging to obtain a representative sample using probability sampling techniques. The population of interest consists of manufacturing companies in Cameroon.

Sample Size

The sample size as calculated using the Taro Yamane formula, a simpler method, was used to figure out the sample size (Israel, 1992). The sample size required will depend on the size of effect that trying to detect (i.e. how strong the relationship is that we are trying to measure) and how much power we want to detect these effects. The simplest rule of thumb is that the bigger the sample size, the better! The reason is that the estimate of R that we get from regression is dependent on the number of predictors, k, and the sample size, N. In fact the expected R for random data is $\frac{K}{N-1}$ and so with small sample sizes random data can appear to show a strong effect. It is all very well knowing that larger samples are better, but researchers usually need some more concrete guidelines (much as we would all love to collect 1000 cases of data it is not always practical). Green (1991) makes two rules of thumb for the minimum acceptable sample size, the first based on whether you want to test the overall fit of your regression model (i.e. test the R²), and the second based on whether you want to test the individual predictors within the model (i.e. test b-values of the model).

If you want to test the model overall, then he recommends a minimum sample size of $50 + 8k$, where k is the number of predictors. So, with five predictors, we would need a sample size of $50 + 40 = 90$. If you want to test the individual predictors then he suggests a minimum sample size of $104 + k$, so again taking the example of 5 predictors we would need a sample size of $104 + 5 = 109$. Of course, in most cases we are interested both in the overall fit and in the contribution of individual predictors, and in this situation Green recommends you calculate both of the minimum sample sizes we have just described, and use the one that has the largest value. Following the five-predictor case, we could consider a sample size of 109 because it is bigger than 90, but it is adjusted by the researcher to 110. This study therefore adopts a sample size of 110 respondents.

Research Instruments

The questionnaire was used to collect data the independent variables in the questionnaire is Green Recruitment and Selection (GRS). Each indicator was measured using a 5-point Likert scale of agreement, with options ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree).

The dependent variable in the questionnaire is Corporate Sustainability (CS), which was measured by seven indicators. Each indicator was measured using a 5-point Likert scale of agreement, with options ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree).

Method of Data Collection

We used Primary data to collect information directly from the source. This data was collected using surveys. Primary data was considered to be more accurate and relevant to the research question as it was collected specifically for the research project at hand.

Data Analysis Procedures and Treatment

Quantitative data was obtained by counting, coding, and keying in Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The data is cleaned once it has been entered into SPSS and coded. Missing values were treated using the software SPSS. Cleaning of the data is the necessary condition

that is fulfilled before subjecting the data to exploratory factor analysis and before exporting the data to Smarts PLS 4 and STATA for further investigations.

Model Specification

Simulating the effects of green recruitment and selection on sustainability of manufacturing companies in Cameroon

Using an effect model, the underlying causal links between green recruitment and selection and corporate sustainability are laid forth. The effect functional form is given by:

$$CS = f(GRS) \quad (1)$$

Where;

CS is corporate sustainability, and

GRS is green recruitment and selection.

Equation 1 shows the direct functional relationship between green recruitment and selection and corporate sustainability.

Figure 1. Hypothesized Model of Corporate Sustainability

Note: PR stands for Paperless recruitment AP is an Application process
OA stands for online advertisement TVI is Telephone/video-based interviews

The pictorial hypothesized model in figure 1. Shows the effect of green recruitment and selection on the sustainability of manufacturing companies in Cameroon is captured by the coefficient β_i . These parameters are technically called regression weight. The forecast errors of the influence of green recruitment and selection on corporate sustainability in manufacturing companies in Cameroon are quantified by the parameter ϵ_1 . For instance, in a structural equation model, the inner model and outer model of measurement are both possible. Both the construct-indicator relationship and the latent construct-latent construct connection are shown in the outer measurement model. Each of the constructs is captured using observed indicators.

Specification of the Econometric Model

$$CS = \beta_1 PR_i + \beta_2 AP_i + \beta_3 OA_i + \beta_4 TVI_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

Where;

CS stands for corporate sustainability

PR stands for Paperless recruitment

AP is Application process

OA stands for online advertisement

TVI is Telephone/video-based interviews

Where 1, 2, 3, and 4 are parameters to which measures the extent to which Paperless recruitment, application process, and online advertisement, telephone/video-based and because no constant has a Z score greater than zero, the models are provided without an intercept. The a priori theoretical predictions about the sign of the coefficients are neutral.

Cronbach's 'Alpha and Construct Reliability

The reliability of a scale may be quantified using a statistic called the Cronbach alpha coefficient. It is a way to measure how strongly one scale item correlates with the others. The recommended value for Cronbach's alpha by Vallis (2003) is 0.7 or higher. In addition, factor loadings on latent constructs will be analysed to evaluate the consistency of each component (Hulland, 1999). If there is more shared variation between the concept and its measures than error variance, then the loadings will be higher. Convergent validity is also shown by loading factors over 0.5.

Findings

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1. Telephone Base Interview, Paperless Recruitment, and Online Advertisement

Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Please rate the level of candidate satisfaction with the paperless recruitment process	7(6.4%)	18(16.4%)	22(20.0%)	34(30.9%)	29(26.4%)
.social media and other digital platforms in enhances the reach and sustainability of your recruitment efforts	5(4.5%)	13(11.8%)	31(28.2%)	33(30.0%)	28(25.5%)
Telephone/video-based interviews have not compromised the quality of our candidate assessments.	7(6.4%)	16(14.5%)	34(30.9%)	30(27.3%)	23(20.9%)

Source: Field Survey, March (2024)

The results in table 1. explain the various aspects of the paperless recruitment process, candidate satisfaction, and its perceived impact on environmental commitments within the company. Regarding candidate satisfaction with the paperless recruitment process, the responses indicate a diverse range of opinions. While a minority of respondents strongly agree (6.4%) or agree (16.4%)

with the process, a significant portion expresses neutral (20.0%) or negative sentiments, with 30.9% disagreeing and 26.4% strongly disagreeing. This suggests a lack of overwhelming satisfaction among candidates, with a notable proportion expressing dissatisfaction with the paperless approach.. Similarly, regarding the utilization of social media and other digital platforms to enhance recruitment reach and sustainability, opinions vary. A small percentage of respondents (4.5% strongly agree and 11.8% agree) perceive digital platforms positively in this regard. However, a substantial number of respondents remain neutral (28.2%), while a considerable portion disagrees (30.0%) or strongly disagrees (25.5%) a notable portion of respondents (30.9%) agree that telephone/video-based interviews have not compromised assessment quality, a comparable percentage (20.9%) strongly disagrees, suggesting apprehension about the effectiveness of remote methods in thoroughly evaluating candidates.

Corporate Sustainability

Table 2. Corporate Sustainability

Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Our company actively implements initiatives to reduce waste and promote recycling.	9(8.2%)	21(19.1%)	26(23.6%)	31(28.2%)	23(20.9%)
Management prioritizes environmental sustainability in our business strategies.	6(5.5%)	19(17.3%)	30(27.3%)	22(20.0%)	33(30.0%)
Our organization invests in renewable energy sources to minimize our carbon footprint.	4(3.6%)	17(15.5%)	28(25.5%)	31(28.2%)	30(27.3%)

From table 2 beginning with the statement, "our company actively implements initiatives to reduce waste and promote recycling," the data indicates that only 8.2% of respondents strongly agree with this assertion, while 19.1% agree. In contrast, a significant 49.1% either disagree or strongly disagree (28.2% disagreeing and 20.9% strongly disagreeing). This substantial level of skepticism suggests that many employees do not perceive the company as effectively engaging in waste reduction and recycling efforts, signaling a need for enhanced visibility and communication of these initiatives. The statement, "Management prioritizes environmental sustainability in our business strategies," also draws mixed responses. Only 5.5% of respondents strongly agree and 17.3% agree, while a notable 50% express disagreement (20% disagreeing and 30% strongly disagreeing).

Outer Loadings Model

Table 3. Outer Loading Factor

	Application process	Corporate Sustainability	Online advertisement	Paperless recruitment	Telephone video-based interviews
ap1	-0.100				
ap2	0.732				
ap3	0.649				
ap4	-0.507				
cs0		0.564			
cs1		0.476			
cs2		0.192			
cs3		0.488			

cs4		0.626			
cs5		0.678			
od1			0.330		
od2			0.639		
od3			0.721		
od4			0.699		
pr1				0.694	
pr2				0.493	
pr3				0.382	
pr4				0.664	
tvb1					0.676
tvb2					0.330
tvb3					0.695
tvb4					0.471

Source: Field Survey, March (2024)

The result in table 4.26 show the outer model loading revealed that attitudes towards paperless recruitment was measured using question item 8 to 11 on the questionnaire, application process was captured using question item 12 to 15 on the questionnaire, online advertisement was measured using question item 16 to 19 on the questionnaire, telephone/video-based interview was measured using question item 20 to 23 on the questionnaire while corporate sustainability was measured using seven question items on the questionnaire, that is, question item 92 to 97. Only question items with factor loadings of approximately 0.5 and above was retained

in the study as it explained 50% of the variance in the component they load under. This outer model loadings factors does not indicate whether the indicators are significant or not. The items retained were furthered subjected to bootstrapping test to obtain the t-statistical value, which indicates whether the indicators are significant or not.

Bootstrapping Outer Loadings Model

Table 4. Bootstrapping Outer Loadings Model (Mean, STDEV, T-Values, P-Values)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ap1 <- Application process	0.519	0.461	0.256	2.024	0.043
ap2 <- Application process	0.425	0.322	0.319	1.332	0.183
ap3 <- Application process	0.577	0.479	0.285	2.025	0.043
ap4 <- Application process	0.500	0.464	0.299	1.672	0.095
cs0 <- Corporate Sustainability	0.575	0.542	0.158	3.637	0.000
cs1 <- Corporate Sustainability	0.509	0.478	0.162	3.134	0.002
cs2 <- Corporate Sustainability	0.219	0.217	0.205	1.065	0.287
cs3 <- Corporate Sustainability	0.584	0.557	0.133	4.388	0.000
cs4 <- Corporate Sustainability	0.552	0.556	0.141	3.913	0.000
cs5 <- Corporate Sustainability	0.600	0.594	0.124	4.828	0.000
od1 <- Online advertisement	0.363	0.337	0.218	1.664	0.096
od2 <- Online advertisement	0.475	0.460	0.177	2.681	0.007
od3 <- Online advertisement	0.804	0.776	0.091	8.800	0.000
od4 <- Online advertisement	0.703	0.673	0.117	5.990	0.000
pr1 <- Paperless recruitment	0.703	0.664	0.157	4.475	0.000
pr2 <- Paperless recruitment	0.475	0.455	0.206	2.309	0.021
pr3 <- Paperless recruitment	0.489	0.470	0.204	2.398	0.017
pr4 <- Paperless recruitment	0.588	0.546	0.181	3.244	0.001
tvb1 <- Telephone video-based interviews	0.371	0.340	0.248	1.498	0.134

tvb2 <- Telephone video-based interviews	0.433	0.405	0.192	2.253	0.024
tvb3 <- Telephone video-based interviews	0.699	0.665	0.129	5.419	0.000
tvb4 <- Telephone video-based interviews	0.643	0.621	0.142	4.522	0.000

Source: Field Survey, March (2024)

The result in table 5 shows that all the indicators outer model T- statistics were all significant at 99% confidence level but for ap2, cs2 and tvb1 which were revealed insignificant. The finding indicates strong validity discriminant. In other words, the questionnaire items loading on the various factors.

Bootstrapping Construct Result

Below is the bootstrapping construct result for green recruitment and selection and corporate sustainability as presented in figure 2.

Figure 2. Bootstrapping Construct Results

Source: Field Survey, March (2024)

SmartPLS provides t-statistics to evaluate the significance of the inner and outer models using a method called bootstrapping (Wong, 2013). Corporate sustainability is the endogenous element in this model, whereas exogenous factors include paperless recruitment, application process, online advertisement, and telephone/video-based interviews. The proposed model was further examined using the estimated t-statistics from bootstrapping. Paperless recruitment, application process, and telephone/video-based interviews were seen to be statistically significant while online advertisement was statistically insignificant. Kutner, Nachtsheim, and Neter (1988) recommend using a threshold t-statistic of 2.0 or higher and a level of significance of 0.05. James, Witten, Hastie and Tibshirani (2013) suggested a threshold t-statistic of 1.96 (which corresponds to a 5% level of

significance) for testing the statistical significance of regression coefficients. In a more recent textbook, Fox and Weisberg (2015) suggested a threshold t-statistic of 1.96 or 2.0 and a level of significance of 0.05 or 0.01. It is worth noting that the choice of threshold t-statistic and level of significance may depend on the specific application and study of the regression analysis as may have been the case in this current study.

Bootstrapping Path Coefficients Results

Results in table 5 present bootstrapping path coefficient result for green recruitment and selection, and corporate sustainability.

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Mean, STDEV, T-Values, P-Values)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Application process -> Corporate Sustainability	0.181	0.206	0.100	1.819	0.069
Online advertisement -> Corporate Sustainability	0.143	0.155	0.094	1.515	0.130
Paperless recruitment -> Corporate Sustainability	0.284	0.297	0.086	3.311	0.001
Telephone video-based interviews -> Corporate Sustainability	0.298	0.305	0.095	3.152	0.002

Source: Field Survey, March (2024)

Application processes were shown to have a positive coefficient value, indicating that they had a favourable impact on corporate sustainability in manufacturing companies Cameroon. The p-value of 0.069 for this finding indicates that it is statistically significant at 10%.

It was discovered that in the manufacturing companies in Cameroon, online advertisement had a positive effects on increasing corporate sustainability. If other factors remain constant, a higher rate of online advertisement in the in manufacturing companies in Cameroon would have a positive impact on efforts to increase corporate sustainability there. This result agrees with our preconceived notion.

It was also shown that paperless recruitment has a positive coefficient value, suggesting that it has a direct role in corporate sustainability in the manufacturing companies in Cameroon. In the manufacturing companies in Cameroon, an increase of one unit in creative conduct would lead to a 0.284 unit increase in corporate sustainability. The significance level at which this result stands is 1%.

In addition, the data analysis showed that in manufacturing companies in Cameroon, telephone video-based interviews had a positive and statistically significant influence on corporate sustainability. This suggests that, all else being equal, a change of telephone video-based interviews unit would result in a 0.298 achievement unit in corporate sustainability in manufacturing companies in Cameroon.

Construct R- Square

Table 6. Construct R- Square

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Corporate Sustainability	0.409	0.387

Source: Field Survey, March (2024)

The results in table 6 show R-square coefficient which is the coefficient of multiple determinations of 0.409 reveals that the independent variables used in the model are able to account for about 40.9% of changes in the dependent variable. Meanwhile the adjusted R-Square value which measures the strength of the model shows that the model is good.

Blindfolding Test Results of Predictive Relevance

Blindfolding Test Results of Predictive Relevance for the Various Latent Constructs present in table 7.

Table 7. Blindfolding Test Results

	Q ² predict	RMSE	MAE
Corporate Sustainability	0.235	0.866	0.680

Source: Field Survey, March (2024)

The overview of the overall results of the blindfolding method (first three lines) is shown in the first section of the default report (Default Report=>Blindfolding=>Results=>Construct Cross validated Redundancy), followed by the results of each blindfolding round. Based on the research of Chin (1998), it seems that a good model shows its worth when Q2 is greater than zero. Therefore, it may be stated that the model has predictive validity in regard to the endogenous latent variables, since its Q2 coefficients for the dependent construct (corporate sustainability) are significantly larger than zero.

Discussion of Findings

The analysis of objective focuses on understanding how green recruitment and selection processes influence corporate sustainability in manufacturing companies in Cameroon. The results from various statistical analyses reveal that specific green recruitment and selection practices have a positive impact on corporate sustainability. Application Process: The positive coefficient value indicates that an efficient and eco-friendly application process significantly enhances corporate sustainability. This aligns with the theoretical frameworks suggesting that sustainable practices in hiring processes can lead to overall organisational sustainability. This is consistent with the Resource-Based View (RBV) theory, which posits that unique resources and capabilities, such as sustainable recruitment processes, can provide firms with a competitive advantage. Green recruitment and selection processes can be viewed as valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable resources that enhance corporate sustainability.

The findings show equally that using online advertisements positively impacts corporate sustainability. This can be theoretically backed by the Institutional Theory, which argues that organisations adopt sustainable practices to gain legitimacy and align with societal norms and values. Online advertisements reduce paper usage and align with societal expectations for environmentally friendly practices.

The positive coefficient for paperless recruitment suggests that eliminating paper in recruitment processes directly contributes to corporate sustainability. The Stakeholder Theory supports this by emphasizing the importance of addressing the interests of all stakeholders, including the environment, in business practices. The data analysis indicates that telephone and video-based interviews significantly influence corporate sustainability. This finding is supported by the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which explains that perceived ease of use and perceived

usefulness of technology lead to its adoption. In this case, using technology for interviews reduces carbon footprint and promotes sustainability.

These findings support earlier research by Krejcie and Morgan (1970), which revealed a significant positive relationship between green recruitment/selection and corporate sustainability. Further, the results corroborate Hadjri, Perizade, and Farla (2019), who established a positive statistical relationship between Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) practices and firm sustainability

The integration of green recruitment and selection practices significantly contributes to corporate sustainability in manufacturing companies in Cameroon. The theoretical frameworks of RBV, Institutional Theory, Stakeholder Theory, and TAM provide a robust foundation for understanding the positive impact of these practices on sustainability

Conclusion

The results regarding green recruitment and selection practices suggest that certain application processes, such as online advertisement and paperless recruitment, have a positive impact on corporate sustainability in manufacturing companies in Cameroon. Furthermore, telephone video-based interviews were found to significantly influence corporate sustainability, indicating the importance of innovative recruitment methods in promoting sustainability within manufacturing firms.

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